

STUDIES IN LONG-CHAIN ACIDS. PART II. ON ALEURITIC ACID (I.)

BY P. C. MITTER AND PHANINDRA CHANDRA DUTTA.

Ethyl 16-acetoxy-10-ketopalmitate has been synthesised as a preliminary to the synthesis of 9:10:16-trihydroxypalmitic acid (aleuritic acid).

Aleuritic acid is one of the important constituents of shellac resin. Its constitution as 9:10:16-trihydroxypalmitic acid has been determined from analytical data, obtained mainly by a study of the products of oxidative degradation (Nagel, *Ber.*, 1927, 60, 605), but no work has been done to prove the constitution and it seemed, therefore, of interest to attempt a synthesis of the substance along lines closely following that of Robinson and Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 175 ; 1926, 2004; 1930, 745).

ω -Phenoxy-pentamethylene bromide was condensed in the usual way with acetoacetic ester to give (I). Here two molecules of acetoacetic ester were taken to prevent the formation of the bi-molecular condensation product which was always an undesirable residue left in the flask after distillation (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 898; *cf.* Robinson, *ibid.*, 1937, 723).

Condensation of this ester with sebacic acid half-ester chloride was carried out in ether solution. The product was directly hydrolysed with dilute alkali. No product was, however, isolated on following the conditions laid down for the hydrolysis of this type of compounds by Robinson and Robinson (*loc. cit.*) and consequently the conditions of Chuang, Tien and Huang (*Ber.*, 1937, 70, 858) were followed. The hydrolysis proceeded slowly in presence of alcohol and it was continuously shaken for 60-70 hours until the whole of neutral matter went into solution. The keto-acid (III), thus obtained, was purified through its sodium salt. Dephenoxylation was carried out by heating with hydrobromic acid and glacial acetic acid for 6 hours (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 49, 1829). The yield from this operation was, however, very poor. The bromoketo-acid, thus obtained, was treated with fused potassium acetate in glacial acetic acid and the acetoxy derivative was isolated as the corresponding ethyl ester by treatment with hydrochloric acid and alcohol. The keto group was, however, found to be very inactive so much so that it gave no semicarbazone. Catalytic reduction of this carbonyl group with Adam's PtO_2 catalyst or Pd-BaSO_4 gave no desired result. Reduction of the carbonyl group was also attempted with sodium amalgam in a current of carbon dioxide, but the ester group was knocked off. Similarly there is considerable possibility of the acetyl group being also knocked off along with the ethyl group. Since the yield during dephenoxylation is very poor, we have in mind to proceed with the corresponding methoxy compound, for it has been shown by Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 269) that such groups could be easily knocked off with satisfactory yield. Another modification which we are contemplating to introduce in the general scheme, is the reduction of the carbonyl group with aluminium isopropoxide according to Lund (*Ber.*, 1937, 70, 1520). To prepare the methoxy-pentamethylene iodide, we have condensed malonic ester with methoxy-trimethylene iodide. (Robinson, *ibid.*, 1937, 61). ω -Methoxyvaleric ester was reduced with sodium and alcohol. This was converted to chloride by thionyl chloride and pyridine and then to iodide by refluxing with sodium iodide in acetone solution (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 269).

It has been proved by condensation with acetone that the hydroxyl groups of the natural acid at 9:10 positions occupy *cis*-configuration and

lately it has been shown that the introduction of the two hydroxyl groups with *cis*-configuration at an unsaturation is only possible by oxidation with hydrogen peroxide in presence of OsO₄ (*Ber.*, 1938, 71, 1483).

The work is being continued.

EXPERIMENTAL.

ω-Phenoxy-pentamethylene-acetoacetic Ester (I).—Pentamethylene bromide, prepared from benzoylpiperidine by the application of von Braun's reaction ("Organic Synthesis", Vol. IX, p. 18), was monophenoxylated under conditions identical to those described for the preparation of phenoxy-trimethylene bromide. To a well-cooled solution of sodium (1.6 g.) in alcohol (20 c.c.) a mixture of the bromo-ether (16 g.) and acetoacetic ester (17 g., 2 mols.) was added and the solution refluxed on a water-bath for 24 hours. It was poured into water and the oil was extracted with ether, washed with sodium bicarbonate and dried (sodium sulphate). On removal of lower boiling fractions, the ester distilled at 180°/3 mm., yield 14 g. It gave a brownish violet colouration with ferric chloride in alcoholic solution. (Found : C, 69.3; H, 8.2. C₁₇H₂₄O₄ requires C, 69.8; H, 8.2 per cent).

ω-Phenoxy-10-ketopalmitic Acid (III).—Sodium (2.5 g.) was pulverised, covered with dry ether and cooled in ice. To this the above ester (29.2 g.) was slowly added with shaking and on allowing to stand overnight, a clear reddish solution was obtained. To this mixture, the half-ester chloride of sebacic acid was added under cooling. A vigorous reaction set in with immediate separation of sodium chloride. The mixture was allowed to stand overnight, refluxed on the water-bath for 1 hour and was then decomposed with ice and washed thoroughly with sodium bicarbonate to remove the excess of half-ester. On removal of ether, a viscous reddish mass was obtained. This crude condensation product was directly hydrolysed by aqueous alcoholic caustic potash under the following conditions :

25.5 G. of this condensation product were added to 180 c.c. of 4% aqueous caustic potash and the mixture was continuously shaken for 60-72 hours until a clear solution was obtained, traces of neutral matter being removed by ether. It was acidified with ice-cold sulphuric acid and the oil separating was thoroughly extracted with ether, the extract dried over sodium sulphate and the ether removed on the water-bath. After the removal of ether the heating was continued until there was no evolution of carbon dioxide. On cooling, the mass solidified in beautiful crystals. Hydrolysis was completed by again heating this mass with 200 c.c. of 10% caustic soda solution for 2 hours on a water-bath. On cooling, crusts of sodium salts

separated on the surface, which were filtered off and decomposed by boiling with hydrochloric acid. On cooling, the acid crystallised out. It was collected and recrystallised from alcohol in shining plates, m.p. 89° , yield 2 g. (Found : C, 72.93 ; H, 9.3. $C_{22}H_{34}O_4$ requires C, 73.03 ; H, 9.1 per cent).

The keto-ester was prepared by passing a stream of dry hydrogen chloride into a cooled solution of the acid in alcohol and on refluxing for 3 hours on a water-bath on the next day. It distilled at $252^{\circ}/2$ mm., m. p. 50° . (Found : C, 74.0 ; H, 9.7. $C_{24}H_{38}O_4$ requires C, 73.8 ; H, 9.5 per cent).

16-Bromo-10-ketopalmitic Acid (IV).—The keto-acid (10 g.) was placed in a 100 c.c. flask fitted with a long fractionating column and glacial acetic acid (20 c.c.) and constant boiling hydrobromic acid (25 c.c.) were added. The mixture was refluxed over a free flame and allowed to distill off at such a rate that the temperature at the head of the fractionating column was maintained between 115° and 120° . More hydrobromic acid was added during heating. The reaction mixture was heated for 5-6 hours and finally the hydrobromic acid was distilled off as far as possible. The mass was cooled and extracted repeatedly with petroleum ether ($50-60^{\circ}$). The white crystalline residue left on evaporation was again crystallised until the m.p. rose to 69° . It was obtained as sandy crystals, m.p. 69° , yield 1.2 g. (Found : Br, 22.3. $C_{16}H_{29}O_3Br$ requires Br, 22.8 per cent).

The white residue left on evaporation of the mother-liquor was again digested with glacial acetic acid and hydrobromic acid when a further quantity of the bromo-acid was obtained.

Ethyl 16-Acetoxy-10-ketopalmitate (VI).—The bromo-acid (2 g.) was refluxed for 24 hours with 1.5 g. of freshly fused potassium acetate and glacial acetic acid (15 c.c.) over a free flame. Potassium bromide separated and was filtered off and acetic acid was removed under water pump. The dark residue was poured into water when flaky crystals separated. They were collected, dried and directly esterified by alcohol and gaseous hydrochloric acid. After pouring into water and washing with sodium bicarbonate, the residue was distilled in vacuum when the keto-ester distilled and solidified as flakes, b. p. $219-20^{\circ}/3$ mm., m.p. $54-55^{\circ}$. (Found : C, 67.9 ; H, 10.6. $C_{20}H_{36}O_5$ requires C, 67.4 ; H, 10.1 per cent).